

ACHIEVEMENTS AND PROSPECTS OF INTERCULTURAL COMMUNICATION

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10820481>

Abstract. *We learn to communicate, act, think, use objects and objects through culture. First of all, we need to understand the meaning of the word "culture". This article covers issues such as culture, typology of cultures, types of communication, oral communication, adaptation to culture, intercultural achievements and conflicts. Nowadays, the issues of ling culturalism related to the concept of language and culture, which attract everyone's attention in the science of linguistics, are being researched by many scientists, but they have not found their solution. This article is noteworthy because it focuses on this issue - the achievements and prospects of intercultural communication.*

Keywords: *culture, social communication, cross-cultural communication, communicative competence, intercultural communication, linguistic competence, sociolinguistic competence, existential competence.*

At a time when different peoples, languages, cultures are mixed, interest in other cultures, respect them, try to understand them learning to approach them with patience is one of the urgent problems.

Relations between language and culture. Language learning is a complex process involving not only alphabet, vocabulary and grammar, but also the content of the text, such as behavior and cultural norms. Thanks to new information technologies, all aspects of intercultural interaction in work processes, daily lifestyles, education and daily communication processes are changing before our eyes. For example, when students are learning a new language, they have the ability to communicate directly with the culture along with the content of the new language and the language features in the process of learning the language. To learn any language, they go through the process of learning not only the language, but also all the features associated with it: place, space, history and culture. Thus, by speaking a language, they can automatically assimilate into the culture of that language, that is, the strength and essence of the relationship between language and culture. Therefore, linguists such as Gao, Tang, and Hu [4,210 p.] expressed a firm opinion that "Language is culture, and these two terms are closely related." Other experts such as Brock and Nagasaka [3,35p] argue that intercultural or pragmatic competence should be considered at all stages of language learning. This program can provide foreign language learners with social skills, because through these skills, students will be able to make social connections and be successful in doing so. Language is used as a means of communication and a unit of culture. In the field of the English language teaching system, there are two opposing views on the relationship between language and culture: the first view emphasizes that language and culture are inextricably linked. This idea is taken from a 2003 paper by Biram and Grandy. "However, the second view is that English language teaching should be individualized from cultural contexts," Sardi's 2002 book argues[4,58]. This popular debate examines whether or not the concepts of language and culture are connected.

Thus, when developing language learning pedagogy, teachers must take into account learning styles and students' abilities, as well as, most importantly, linguistic and cultural diversity. Teaching a foreign language as education in my experience as a student and teacher, as well as in my pedagogical philosophy, is to get rid of the limits of my national living environment and culture. cannot be ignored in language teaching.

The same the rise and prosperity of all countries at that time, the different nationalities in that country and people agree, together, with alternative mutual relations, as well as in friendship depends on the behavior.

Religious and cultural tolerance - people of different nationalities learn each other's language, religion, lifestyle, customs, etc. It means respecting traditions, national-cultural heritage, appreciating their honor, dignity, and decoration. This is religious and cultural tolerance, peace ensures stability.

In conclusion, I can say that this article attempts to focus on the relationship between language and culture, to understand why the teaching of culture should be an integral part of the foreign language curriculum. An in-depth analysis of the literature was aimed at contributing to a better understanding of culture and its important aspects in the process of foreign language learning. Language learning or teaching is aimed at developing students' communicative competence, which is not limited to knowing and understanding the grammatical, lexical and phonological features of the studied foreign language, but also learning or teaching the culture of that language. should also deal with. According to some scholars such as Politzer and Brusk, "Language and culture are the same concepts." [2,14] Teachers should not only present and describe to their students how intercultural communication occurs, but also use practical tools such as games or simulations that can be implemented in intercultural communication. Effective intercultural and interpersonal (interpersonal) communication is impossible without adequate understanding of them. The goal of learning a foreign language together with culture is to analyze communication issues with a focus on language and culture, to facilitate communication between different cultures and to prevent conflicts. The concepts of language and culture are interrelated and cannot be separated from each other because language itself is culture. Teaching culture allows students to increase their knowledge of people's ways of life, attitudes, beliefs and values, and language skills. Evidence shows that students can be more successful in language learning if teachers introduce cultural awareness into their language teaching methods, meaning that students can do so not only in language but also in learning. they will have all the necessary resources about the languages they are learning. After all, culture is a concept that appeared before language. The focus on languages and their learning in our country. Because of the wide opportunities created for young people, young people are modern technologies they are keeping up with the times using their opportunities and this is a clear example are our achievements in all fields today.

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